

Notes

Studies on Potential Pesticides, Part V. Synthesis of Some New Aryl Ureas and Thioureas and their Insecticidal Activity

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THE insecticidal and acaricidal properties of Imidan, (O, O-dimethyl-S-phthalimido methyl phosphorodithioate) are well known and it controls codling moths, alfa alfa, weevil and suppresses spider mites. Cattle grub is totally controlled using Imidan¹. Torak (S-(2-chloro-1-phthalimido ethyl) O, O-diethyl phosphorodithioate), a product of Hercules Incorporation is a promising insecticide and acaricide for controlling thrips and mites on citrus². Potential insecticidal, fungicidal and acaricidal properties of phthalimides of diversified chemical constitution have been confirmed by various workers³⁻⁹. The insecticidal, bactericidal and herbicidal activity of various ureas and thioureas have been reported recently¹⁰⁻¹⁴. The impetus of these important findings led us to synthesise several new ureas and thioureas with the active phthalimido nucleus which may not be highly toxic and yet may possess insecticidal activity.

N₁-phthalimido acetyl/2-propionyl-N₃-aryl ureas were obtained by condensing phthalimido acetyl/2-propionyl chloride with appropriate aryl ureas. In addition, thioureas have been obtained from corresponding isothiocyanate and appropriate amines. The intermediate phthalimido acetyl/2-propionyl isothiocyanates were prepared from the corresponding acyl chlorides and ammonium thiocyanates.

Experimental

(All melting points are uncorrected)

Phthalimido acetic or 2-propionic acid was prepared by the fusion of phthalic anhydride with glycine or dl-alanine respectively¹⁵. Phthalimido acetyl/2-propionyl chlorides were obtained by usual methods¹⁶. Aryl ureas were obtained by known methods^{17,18}.

N₁-phthalimido acetyl/2-propionyl-N₃-aryl ureas: To a solution of 0.01 mole of phthalimido acetyl/2-propionyl chloride in 30 ml of sodium dry benzene was added 0.01 mole of appropriate urea and the mixture was refluxed on water bath for 5 hrs. The benzene was removed under reduced pressure and the crude solid was washed with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution. The solid thus obtained was recrystallised from ethanol. All the compounds were beautiful white cotton like material and satisfactory analysis have been obtained for all the new compounds.

TABLE I—SUBSTITUTED PHTHALIMIDO ACYL UREAS AND THIOUREAS

Compd. No.	R	Ar	X	M.P. °C	Yield	Molecular Formula	Analysis % Nitrogen	
							Calcd.	Found
1.	H	2-OCH ₃	O	256	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₅	11.89	11.67
2.	-CH ₃	3-CH ₃	O	175	55	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄	11.97	11.92
3.	-CH ₃	4-CH ₃	O	148	58	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄	11.97	11.84
4.	-CH ₃	2-OCH ₃	O	228	55	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₅	11.44	11.23
5.	-CH ₃	4-OCH ₃	O	138	60	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₅	11.44	11.44
6.	H	3-CH ₃	S	210	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄ S	11.90	11.76
7.	H	2-Cl	S	218	60	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₃ O ₄ ClS	11.26	11.13
8.	H	3-Cl	S	201	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₃ O ₄ ClS	11.26	11.32
9.	H	2, 4-di Cl	S	221	60	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₄ Cl ₂ S	10.29	10.06
10.	H	4-F	S	192	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₃ O ₄ FS	11.76	11.74
11.	H	4-Br	S	211	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₃ O ₄ BrS	10.05	9.83
12.	H	1-CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	S	205	62	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄ S	11.92	11.84
13.	H	4-biphenyl	S	210	65	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄ S	10.12	10.03
14.	-CH ₃	H	S	188	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄ S	11.89	11.73
15.	-CH ₃	2-CH ₃	S	140	60	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄ S	11.44	11.44
16.	-CH ₃	3-CH ₃	S	140	65	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄ S	11.44	11.36
17.	-CH ₃	4-CH ₃	S	180	65	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄ S	11.44	11.18
18.	-CH ₃	2-OCH ₃	S	155	60	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₅ S	10.97	11.08
19.	-CH ₃	4-OCH ₃	S	140	60	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₅ S	10.97	10.78
20.	-CH ₃	2-OC ₂ H ₅	S	156	60	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄ S	10.58	10.36
21.	-CH ₃	2-Cl	S	135	62	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₄ ClS	10.85	10.76
22.	-CH ₃	3-Cl	S	115	64	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₄ ClS	10.85	10.68
23.	-CH ₃	4-Cl	S	160	66	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₄ ClS	10.85	10.49
24.	-CH ₃	3-NO ₂	S	162	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₅ S	14.07	13.88
25.	-CH ₃	4-NO ₂	S	188	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₅ S	14.07	14.02
26.	-CH ₃	4-Br	S	140	62	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₄ BrS	9.72	9.68
27.	-CH ₃	1-CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	S	135	63	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄ S	11.44	11.28
28.	-CH ₃	4-F	S	159	65	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄ FS	11.32	11.19
29.	-CH ₃	4-biphenyl	S	171	65	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄ S	9.76	9.63

*N*₁-phthalimido acetyl/2-propionyl-*N*₈-aryl thio-ureas : To a 250 ml three necked flask equipped with a mechanical stirrer and reflux condenser and a dropping funnel, were charged 0.01 mole of phthalimido acetyl/2-propionyl chloride and 30 ml dry benzene. To the vigorously stirred solution was added drop by drop a solution of 0.01 mole of ammonium thiocyanate in 10 ml dry benzene over a period of 15 min. The isothiocyanate thus obtained was made to react without isolation with appropriate amine (0.01 mole) by refluxing for 3 hr. The mixture was poured in crushed ice and the crude product was filtered and washed several times with water. The product was recrystallised from ethanol.

The m. p., yield and analytical data are recorded in Table 1.

Insecticidal activity : The insecticidal activity was evaluated against adult male flies (*Musca domestica* L.) as the test insect following the method of Nash¹⁹. The compounds were dissolved in acetone and the acetone solution applied at a dosage of 0.001 mole per fly. With every sample, three experiments, each consisting of 20 flies were performed and the treated insects were kept under observation for 24 hr. The average results were recorded taking Heptachlor and Toxaphene as standard.

Compound No. 13 only at 1% concentration afforded 50% mortality against *Musca domestica* L.

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Studies on Hydroxamic Acids : Part II. Separation and Quantitative Determination of Yttrium with *N-m-Tolyl-m-Nitrobenzohydroxamic Acid*

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IN connection to our earlier work¹⁻⁸, this communication deals with the separation and quantitative determination of yttrium with *N-m-tolyl-m-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid*. Experimental results and discussion given below.

Experimental

Chemicals : All the chemicals used were of the G.R. and AnalaR grade of E. Merck and B. D. H. respectively.

Reagent : The reagent *N-m-Tolyl-m-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid* was synthesized by the procedure recommended by Agrawal and Tandon⁶, m. p. 118° (reported 118°). The purity of the reagent was established by elemental analysis T. L. C., I. R. and U. V. Spectra.

Metal solution : The aqueous stock solution of yttrium was prepared by dissolving 0.3830 g of yttrium nitrate hexahydrate in 100 ml of distilled water and its final concentration was determined volumetrically⁷.

Masking agent : A 1% of masking agent solutions of KCN, Citrate-oxalate and Mg-EDTA were prepared by dissolving their requisite amount in distilled water.

Procedure

In a litre beaker an aliquot of yttrium solution and 500 ml distilled water were heated to 60° on a water bath. Then 20 ml of the reagent solution in ethanol was added dropwise, with constant stirring. The desired pH for the precipitation of yttrium (5.7 to 6.5) was adjusted by using 0.1M solution of ammonium hydroxide and of 0.1 M nitric acid. The granular precipitate so obtained was digested for 30 min. on a water bath, filtered through a sintered glass crucible

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